

A four-pronged approach to support students in large classes - combining safeness, sense of belonging, primary school strategies with EdTech for a successful approach.

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Abstract

Large classes at university level conjure up an image of bored students, lost in a multitude of disengaged faces. The lecturer is at the front of the room, sharing their expertise with the masses. However, this is not an engaging way to learn, and not all large classes look like this. This paper shows how an approach that combines fostering a sense of belonging, a safe space for questions, and a basic strategy from the primary school context (think-pair-share) with the use of educational technology can result in engaged students and successful teaching, learning, and assessment. The discipline is computer science with a class of 180 students, but the approach could be applied in any discipline. It involves the academic creating a safe environment for students and scaffolding their independent learning by providing digital resources that enable them to self-assess and prepare for credit-bearing assessments in the module.

Keywords: *Large Classes; Belonging; EdTech.*

1. Introduction

Large classes at the university level can be initially overwhelming for students. They may have seen images of bored students, lost in a multitude of disengaged faces. The lecturer is at the front of a large lecture theatre, sharing their expertise with the masses and being apart from them. However, this is not an engaging way to learn, and not all large classes look like this. This paper shows how an approach that combines fostering a sense of belonging, a safe space for questions and a basic strategy from the primary school context (think-pair-share) with the use of educational technology, can result in engaged students and successful teaching, learning and assessment. The discipline discussed in this paper comes from computer science and is a computer systems module with 180 students. However, the approach could be applied in any discipline. It involves the academic creating a safe environment for students and scaffolding their independent learning by providing digital resources that enable them to self-assess and prepare for credit-bearing assessments in the module.

2. Literature Review

Large classes exist for a variety of reasons, but one of the most common ones is that, in theory, there are economies of scale (see Hornsby & Osman (2014) for an overview). However, as Cuseo (2007) and Allais (2014) point out, this may actually be self-defeating. Despite this, class sizes continue to increase as the perceived economic benefits outweigh the disadvantages. However, all is not lost. There are strategies that can be used to facilitate teaching and learning in large classes (Mulryan-Kyne, 2010). There may be fun and joy associated with large classes (e.g. Ward, 2021) and teaching with care is also an option (Straits, 2007). Different tools and techniques can be used to make these large classes more human and to ensure a positive learning environment for students. One thing to note is that more effort is required on the part of the lecturer to ensure that this happens. Where a lecturer may be able to 'wing it' with a smaller class, this is not the case with large classes, where if something goes wrong, it goes wrong at scale. This does not imply that the lecturer cannot be spontaneous, but rather that they need to have a sense beforehand of how things will play out.

Computer science is a discipline that tends to have large classes. The perceived 'wisdom' is that computer science can be taught to many students at once. However, computer science is a challenging discipline and has one of the highest failure rates across any discipline at the university level (Long & Harrington, 2019), although there has been a slight improvement in recent years (Bennedsen & Caspersen, 2019). Unlike other subjects, many students elect to study computer science at the university level without prior knowledge of the subject, although the situation is changing with the increase in the number

of schools teaching computer science at second level across the world. This has several consequences, ones that are magnified in the context of large classes. Firstly, students feel overwhelmed with the new concepts and terms that they have to learn, and they feel uncomfortable asking questions in a large lecture theatre. Secondly, they see that other students seem to know the material already and feel that they are already falling behind. Thirdly, they may not realise that these students have already studied the material before and have not ‘magically’ understood what the lecturer was explaining, and it is not because they lack the (non-existent) computer science ‘gene’. Fourthly, they may fall behind if they do not understand a concept during a lecture.

Sense of belonging is very important in any learning context, and this holds true for computing (Runa et al., 2024; Runa et al., 2025). The stereotypical image of a computer science student in many, but not all, geographical regions of the world, is that of an introverted male student who prefers to work alone rather than with others. However, it is important for students to be connected with other students and to see themselves as future computer scientists and thus, activities that provide them with opportunities to learn about their fellow students and to interact with them in a non-threatening manner are important.

Teachers at primary school use a think-pair-strategy on a regular basis. Students think about a question and maybe come up with an answer or an idea. They then share their ideas with the person beside them, and then there is time for the class as a whole to share their ideas and thoughts. This approach can also work well at Higher Education level, but is generally not used that often - perhaps because the students are now perceived as adults and the pressure to rush through content.

Self-assessment can be helpful for students to check on their own learning (e.g. Andrade, 2019), and university students understand the purpose of self-assessment and why they should avail of it (Ratminingsih et al., 2018). Formative self-assessment provides students with an opportunity to test their own knowledge, highlight areas for improvement, get immediate feedback, experience early success, retake tests numerous times and catch up on material if they have missed a lecture. These benefits can help increase a student’s sense of belonging by ensuring that they have resources to keep them on track and reassure them across the semester. Thangaraj et al. (2023) provide an overview of formative assessment in computer science.

Large class researchers (e.g. Hornsby, 2020; Arvanitakis, 2021; Felten & Farrell, 2024) outline practical active learning strategies to create a welcoming class environment that contributes to equitable student learning and well-being. Combining the initial class survey, the safe space for questions, think-pair-share and supportive self-assessments helps to enact these strategies in this module.

3. Description of the Teaching and Learning Context

The example presented in this paper relates to a first-year, first-semester introductory module on computer systems to a class of approximately 180 computer science and data science students. The students have two 1-hour classes a week for 12 weeks. At the start of the module, there is a class 'getting to know us' survey which is on the module's Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) page. Each student has to chat with the person beside them and ask the survey questions in turn to each other. The questions are straightforward, for example, "where are you from", "where will you live during term", "how will you commute to college", "how long will it take to travel to college", and "have you studied computer science before college". This means that students will at least talk to one other person in the class at the start of the module. When the students see the overall results for the class, it gives them a sense of who their peers are. They will see that there are people from the same place as them. They will see that there are other students who have the same living/commuting arrangements as them. They will also see what percentage of the class has studied computer science before they came to college. This means that when the lecturer refers to the fact that some students may have studied this before, they know that it is based on information provided by the students themselves and may help to explain why some students seem to 'get' concepts before others. It does not mean that these students are smarter; it is just that they have already learned the concept. This is an assessment for learning (AfL) strategy, whereby students assess characteristics of the class profile to help them situate themselves within that context. This AfL strategy allows the educator to harness the overall class profile to make connections for the students, particularly at the start of the module, but also throughout the semester.

3.1 Safe space to ask questions

Another important element is creating a safe space for students to ask questions. At the start of the module, the lecturer sets out four points that will prevail throughout the module. These are 1) You will not be made fun of if you ask a question 2) The lecturer will repeat your question, so you do not need to shout 3) Often your question will be rephrased for clarity 4) By asking a question, you are probably helping at least 10 other students in the class with the same question but who are afraid to ask it - so thank you for asking. This sets the tone of the module and words to alleviate fears that students might have that they would ask a 'stupid' question. Explicitly stating these points emphasises to the students that the lecturer is aware of the difficulties in asking questions in a large class and reassuring them that they will be supported if and when they do ask questions.

3.2 Think, pair, share approach

Three of the topics in this module are numerate in nature. Students have to work out converting numbers from one number system to another, simply logical equations and work with different types of data representations. The format for these topics is that the lecturer provides an explanation of the topic and a simple example. Students are then asked to work out a simple example themselves first (think), before comparing their answer with their neighbour (pair) and then checking that their answer is the correct one (share). This approach enables students to test their own understanding first and then see what their peers are doing. It can be reassuring for students to see how they perform compared to others in the class. While they are doing this, the lecturer can move about the lecture theatre, gently checking on how students are working through the task, providing support and feedback where required and noting any consistent problems faced by students. This enables the lecturer to explain key features to the class as a whole, without zooming in on a particular student. Students are reassured that they may not be the only ones with difficulties and that they will not be ridiculed for not getting it right the first time.

3.3 Self-Assessment Resources

The students on this module have access to a range of digital resources, including PDF files, short videos, screencasts and self-assessment quizzes on the university's VLE. The self-assessments cover a range of topics but are primarily provided to support three numerative assessments of the seven assessment topics. The other four assignments are descriptive in nature, and there is a different teaching, learning and assessment approach for those assignments. While some may consider seven assignments a lot for a 12-week module, consistent feedback from students is that they like the assessment approach - the assessments are worth 15% each (except for assessment 1, which is worth 10%). The assessments are closely linked to what they are learning, and they can understand the reason behind the assessments. They find this approach to be less stressful than larger assessments. This approach has worked well for this module for many years, but this may not hold for other types of modules. The self-assessments for the three numerative topics are exactly the same in format as the actual credit-bearing assessments - the only difference is that the values in each question are different. This allows the students to practice the test in advance and can help to relieve stress related to an unknown assessment. Logs from the VLE show that students do practice on these self-assessment quizzes, often multiple times, so they are used and they do have value for the students.

4. Reflections

The four-pronged approach adopted in this first-year module has worked well for many years. Creating a safe space at the start of the module and maintaining it throughout the module means that students are not afraid of the lecturer. After a week or two, the students are quite happy to ask questions, which is not always the case in a large class. It is important to continue to encourage and cultivate students' questions and to consistently show that they will be treated with respect at all times. Establishing the class profile at the start of the module means that the students are aware that there are students with a range of prior knowledge or none in the class, and that is why some topics are explained in more detail than some students need. It means that when the lecturer sometimes appears to 'over-explain' something, it is probably for the benefit of students who have not studied the material before. The think-pair-share approach works as it gives the students an opportunity to try something themselves without fear, and they know that they will see the solution shortly afterwards anyway. The students enjoy working out the answer themselves and do not despair if they cannot solve it. They know they will be able to look at their neighbour's answer or get help from them. They know that the lecturer will give them the answer anyway once they have had a chance to solve it for themselves. They know that there are self-assessments they can do online to check their own understanding of the topic in their own time. They know that doing these self-assessments will help them to prepare for the credit-bearing assessments on the same topics, but also enable them to check their own knowledge and understanding of the topics so that they can better understand the lecture contents. This means that students are less likely to fall behind, especially if they miss a lecture - they know they can catch up with the self-assessment quizzes.

This four-pronged approach also works well for the lecturer and this module. There were initially some challenges when implementing these approaches, mainly to do with the lecturer's confidence. What if the students did not want to talk to another student? What if they did not believe the lectures were a safe space to ask questions? What if they were embarrassed to share their solutions with a peer? What if they found the self-assessment quizzes too easy or too hard? However, it turns out that students do want to talk to other students. Consistently demonstrating that it is safe to ask questions in class actually works. Students enjoy chatting with other students about their solutions (and different solutions are fine). Students enjoy doing the self-assessment quizzes, with some students repeating them many times (they persevere until they get 100% in the quizzes).

Combining these approaches enables the lecturer to teach the students while interacting with them on a human level - even with 180 students in the class. The classes are generally enjoyable and rewarding - the lecturer enjoys teaching the students, and there is consistently positive feedback from students over many years. Delivering content is relatively easy - helping students learn, getting and keeping them engaged in a large class is

a challenge. While some elements of this approach may be specific to the module (e.g. the numerate topics), the general approach could work well in other modules with large numbers of students and make them feel involved and not just another face in crowd. Currently, the lecturer has a Students as Partners in Assessment (SaPiA) approach (Ní Bheoláin et al., 2020) in the module where students are given a lot of choice in assignments. Strengthening this approach via co-creation of assessments with students might be another way to deepen engagement and increase a sense of belonging.

5. Conclusion

Being a student in a large class can be daunting, especially for first-year students in the first semester of university. Fostering a sense of belonging and a safe space for questions can help alleviate some of the students' fears. Giving students time to think and share their work with their peers can show students that they can do well and that not everybody gets everything right all of the time. Providing them with digital resources to self-assess their own knowledge can be invaluable for students when there are limited opportunities to have individual consultations with the lecturer to check their understanding of a topic. Successful teaching and learning in large classes is possible and, with the right approach, can be enjoyable and beneficial for both the lecturers and the students.

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